

A Survey on Asymmetric Link Problem in MANET

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Abstract – *Ad hoc network links are often asymmetric due to heterogeneity in the transmission power of devices, non-uniform environmental noise, and other signal propagation phenomenon. Unfortunately routing protocols for mobile ad hoc networks typically work well only in bidirectional networks. This paper first presents a simulation study quantifying the impact of asymmetric links on network connectivity and routing performance. A framework called BRA provides a bidirectional abstraction of the asymmetric network to routing protocols and provides the optimistic route in ad hoc network. BRA works by maintaining multi hop reverse routes for unidirectional links. BRA finds reverse routes through an algorithm called the reverse distributed bellman Ford algorithm and provides three new abilities: Improved connectivity by taking advantage of the unidirectional links, reverse route forwarding of control packets to enable off-the-shelf routing protocols and detection packet loss on unidirectional links.*

Keywords: *BRA, RDBFA, Bellman Ford, Routing, Asymmetric network, MANET.*

I. Introduction

The fundamental problem in mobile ad hoc networks is asymmetric or unidirectional links that arise in the network for several reasons: Devices transmitting with different powers explicitly causes unidirectional links, Irregular links becoming unidirectional due to random irregularities in signal propagation, Unidirectional links created by external noise sources. When the devices transmit the packets with the same power, the packet reception is affected by the noise sources near to the devices and creates unidirectional links. Finally other intractable factors such as barriers and environmental conditions that affect signal propagation also lead to asymmetry. This asymmetric links harmfully affect routing in several ways: Connectivity, Routing, Link layer services [2].

Asymmetric networks have fundamentally different connectivity than bidirectional networks. Two nodes may be connected through one or more unidirectional links requiring an alternative path in the reverse direction. While bidirectional connectivity can often be quite good, it may get worse suddenly and cut-off several bidirectional routes leading to a poorly connected network. A substantial percentage of unidirectional links have short path connecting them in the reverse direction. Unidirectional links with short reverse paths significantly increases the stability of the routes and leads to better connectivity overall without significant overhead.

Next standard routing protocols often fail to function efficiently in an asymmetric network. TOR was primarily designed for bidirectional networks and hence breaks down in the presence of unidirectional links. AODV is a routing protocol that avoids the unidirectional links and route the data only in the bidirectional links. DS protocol

has the capability to include unidirectional links in their routes through expensive mechanisms that provide significantly decreased throughput in asymmetric networks [2][8].

Considering the link layer services, unidirectional links create problems at the lower layers such as the data link and the MAC layers. Common MAC level schemes for congestion avoidance and packet loss recovery fail for unidirectional links. Moreover other useful services such as detection of link breaks and discovery of new neighbors provided by some MAC protocol become unavailable to the routing protocols.

Therefore this paper focus on impact of asymmetric links on network connectivity and routing performance and its solutions proposed in the literature.

II. Routing Protocols for Asymmetric Link

Distributed Bellman Ford Algorithm

It is well known distance vector algorithm to obtain the shortest routes between pairs of nodes in a bidirectional network [6]. This algorithm has practical advantages because it works asynchronously and is guaranteed to converge eventually if the network is not partitioned and remains stable for sufficient time. In this algorithm, each node broadcast its currently known distance, node tag and sequence number embedded with IP option header to identify the acknowledged packets. They maintain separate sequence numbers for each pair of nodes in the locality. The sequence number is set to 0 whenever nodes discover each other in the locality and incremented upon each message transfer. If the acknowledgements are not received in time, nodes retransmit each packet. If a node does not receive an acknowledgement even after retransmission, it notifies the routing protocol about the

failure of packet delivery [10]. The timeout value for receiving an acknowledgement is set proportional to the number of links traversed by the packet and the acknowledgement. Thus if a packet is sent along a direct link A to B with r hop reverse route, then the time out is proportional to $r+1$. The timeout for a packet sent on a direct link is specified by the `ack_timeout` parameter.

Zone Routing Protocol (ZRP)

Since the routing protocols for mobile ad hoc networks have to face the challenge of frequently changing topology, low transmission power and asymmetric links, both reactive and proactive routing protocols prove to be inefficient under these circumstances. The Zone Routing Protocol combines the advantages of the proactive and reactive approaches by maintaining up-to-date topological map of a zone centered on each node [4][9]. Within the zone, routes are immediately available. For destinations outside the zone, ZRP employs a route discovery procedure which can benefit from the local routing information of the zones.

Reverse Distributed Bellman Ford Algorithm (RDBFA)

This algorithm is a modified version of the BRA. As the name implies, RDBFA operates by reversing the direction of route discovery i.e each node aims to find the shortest distance from other nodes to itself rather than from itself to other nodes. At periodic intervals, each node broadcasts to all its out-neighbors a distance-vector message containing the shortest paths of its knowledge from other nodes to itself. A node receiving a distance vector from one of its neighbors extracts the reverse route and follows it. RDBFA provides improved connectivity by taking advantage of the unidirectional links, reverse route forwarding of control packets to enable off-the-shelf routing protocol, detection of packet loss on unidirectional links.

Bidirectional Routing Abstraction (BRA)

In contrast to the ZRP which is proposed for protocol specific solutions for network asymmetry, a general purpose framework called Bidirectional Routing Abstraction (BRA) is proposed [1]. It has some advantages over ZRP. First it enables routing protocols not equipped to handle asymmetry to function with minimal changes. Second it eases protocol design by removing the responsibility of handling asymmetry from the designers of new routing protocols. Finally it creates an opportunity for a more suitable and efficient solution to handle asymmetry. For instance, BRA optimizes its cost benefit tradeoff by supporting asymmetric routing only in regions of poor connectivity and only to the extent required to improve connectivity.

It is a framework that provides improved connectivity and routing performance in asymmetric networks. BRA seeks to improve the efficiency of of-the-shelf routing protocols typically designed for bidirectional networks to function efficiently on asymmetric networks. To that end, BRA provides a bidirectional abstraction of the underlying unidirectional links. The central feature of BRA is an adaptive and scalable technique to maintain reverse routes for unidirectional links.

BRA takes the approach of discovering and maintaining reverse paths for unidirectional links. It makes use of RDBFA which efficiently searches for reverse routes in a bounded search region around each node. BRA keeps the overhead of maintaining reverse routes low by dynamically adjusting the size of the search region and thereby the length of the reverse route. OBRA provides three critical functionalities to facilitate routing in asymmetric network. First it improves connectivity between nodes by finding new or better routes through unidirectional links. Second, it provides reverse route forwarding for unidirectional links which makes them appear as bidirectional links. This abstraction enables routing protocols to send control packets in the reverse direction as it would on symmetric networks. Finally, it implements critical functionalities that MAC and link layers are often unable to provide asymmetric networks [3][7].

BRA is not completely transparent that is a routing protocol layered on top of BRA is expected to be aware of the nature of links they are routing over. This non-transparency allows routing protocols to use the services of BRA intelligently and only upon necessity. For instance, a routing protocol that cannot distinguish whether two nodes are connected through a direct link or a multi hop reverse route might mistake the reverse route for a fast, direct hop route and route packets through the longer route, such an action may increase the cost of routing and introduces additional congestion in the network and decrease the overall throughput of the system [2][8]. It offers reverse route forwarding, reliable packet delivery and link status monitoring .

Reverse route forwarding service is intended to enable routing protocols to send control packets over the reverse route of a unidirectional link instead of through an alternative separately discovered and maintained route. Similarly the reverse path is also used to send notifications about lost or broken paths [5]. BRA's reverse route forwarding provides these abilities on asymmetric paths and helps routing protocols to operate in the same manner on asymmetric networks.

Reliable packet delivery is another service provided by BRA for unidirectional links where the MAC layer schemes fail. BRA uses multi hop acknowledgements and retransmissions for packets sent on both unidirectional links and reverse routes. A packet's destination node

sends an acknowledgement back to the source node upon packet reception. The acknowledgement is sent through the reverse routes for packets received on the direct link, while an acknowledgement for reverse routed packets is sent through the direct link.

BRA extends the functionality of asymmetric networks to perform link status monitoring for reverse route maintenance through periodic messages. It simply exports the link status changes discovered to the routing protocol. A routing protocol can use BRA to check whether a link is broken. A node declares the broken link under any one of two conditions: 1) The node A is unaware of any route from B to itself, 2) A packet transmission to B is failed. The first condition implies that there is no reverse route from B to A and therefore the link is not suitable for routing. The second condition implies that either the direct link or the reverse link route is currently broken.

AODV over BRA

Routing with BRA is straightforward. AODV requires only one key modification to use BRA. It needs to send the control packets such as the route reply packets (RREP) and the route error packets (REER) through reverse route forwarding. AODV may choose shortest path solely based on the length of the forward path as it would on a bidirectional network. Alternatively, it might benefit from including the length of the reverse routes into path selection metric. Otherwise, route request broadcast (RREQ) and data forwarding takes place in the same manner as on bidirectional networks. AODV derives many key benefits from OBRA. First it is able to find additional routes not present in the bidirectional view of the network. Second, it does not require the blacklisting mechanism to identify and isolate unidirectional links. Indeed BRA with locality radius can provide the same functionality as a black list. Finally it can reduce data forwarding delay by finding shorter routes including unidirectional links. Note that reverse route forwarding of RREPs may induce an additional delay in receiving route replies at the source and increase the latency for route discovery.

III. Conclusion

BRA provides routing protocols with the familiar bidirectional abstraction that they are typically designed for and thus enables them to operate efficiently on asymmetric networks. Internally however, it actively uses both unidirectional and bidirectional links to find asymmetric routes more effectively than conventional techniques and find new asymmetric routes substantially increasing the reach ability of the network and find alternate routes with shorter path length.

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